

EFFECTIVENESS OF PLANT EXTRACTS ON BONE HISTOPATHOLOGY OF OSTEOPOROSIS-INDUCED RATS AND MICE: A REVIEW

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Osteoporosis is a common disease that affects millions of patients worldwide, especially Indonesia. The results of research by the Indonesian Osteoporosis Association together with the White Paper, reported that there were 32.3% of women and 28.8% of men over 50 years of age suffering from osteoporosis. The risk of fracture due to osteoporosis is around 40% - 50% in women and 13% - 22% in men (Kemenkes RI, 2020). Osteoporosis disease mostly affects women, however men still have a risk of developing osteoporosis disease. Just like in women, osteoporosis in men is also influenced by estrogen. The difference is that men do not experience menopause, so osteoporosis comes more slowly (Ramadhani, 2022). Menopause is a natural biological stage in a woman's life characterized by the cessation of menstruation due to ovarian aging and usually occurs between the ages of 40 and 58 years. During this time, the ovaries fail to produce ovarian follicles, eventually leading to estrogen deficiency. The resulting hormonal imbalance leads to an increase in a number of health problems, one of which is an increased risk of osteoporosis (Park et al., 2020). In elderly women, there is an increase in the rate of bone remodeling process and also a negative remodeling balance (meaning that resorption occurs more than formation). This leads to bone loss and impaired bone microarchitecture. In elderly men, aging causes a decrease in bone formation and leads to low bone turnover and ends in osteoporosis (Bhattarai et al., 2020).

Osteoporosis is influenced by several factors, including age and gender, and is divided into primary and secondary osteoporosis. Primary osteoporosis includes post-menopausal osteoporosis characterized by a decrease in estrogen production leading to bone loss. Meanwhile, secondary osteoporosis is caused by disease or drug exposure characterized by decreased bone function due to malabsorption, glucocorticoid use, hyperparathyroidism, hypogonadism or excessive alcohol consumption (Kim et al., 2021). Glucocorticoids (GC) are used in clinical practice for their anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory effects. However, the therapeutic use of GCs has an impact on bone loss. Previous studies have shown that long-term administration of GCs resulted in the development of osteoporosis in approximately 50% of patients with asthma. In addition, clinical studies have shown that low-dose GC inhalation therapy or high-dose oral GC therapy, especially with dexamethasone causes bone loss in humans (Zhang et al, 2016). Long-term GC therapy causes complex effects on bone. Rapid initial bone loss is followed by a slow, constant and long-lasting decrease in bone mass (Hachemi et al., 2018).

In addition to glucocorticoid effects, the process of ovariectomy also induces osteoporosis. Ovariectomy is a preclinical model for postmenopausal osteoporosis. This experimental model is characterized by bone loss similar to osteoporosis in postmenopausal women (do Nascimento et al., 2024). In the ovariectomy process, the ovaries of adult female rats are surgically removed which causes a rapid decrease in estrogen levels and mimics the natural changes that occur during menopause in humans. This model is popular in research, as it is reliable, stable, repeatable, and has a high success rate in inducing bone loss similar to that seen in early postmenopausal women (Sun and Lin, 2024). Glucocorticoid and ovariectomy-induced osteoporosis treatments such as bisphosphonates, estrogens, and denosumab have serious drawbacks because the duration of treatment is much longer than the time of post-fracture mortality. In addition, the various side effects

of these drugs make them unviable for long-term use (Shih et al., 2022). The use of herbal plants as an alternative to natural medicine is widely used today because the potential secondary metabolite compounds they contain show significant effectiveness against various diseases, including osteoporosis.

Secondary metabolite compounds are small organic molecules derived from primary metabolites during plant metabolism. The chemical properties and composition of metabolites in plants vary among species. Most of the metabolites in plant natural products are secondary metabolites. Secondary metabolites are of interest due to their structural diversity and potential as drug candidates (Twaij and Md, 2022). Secondary metabolites used as single compounds or mixtures, are drugs that can be effective and safe even when synthetic drugs fail. They can even amplify or synergize the effects of other compounds in treatment (Seca and Diana, 2019). Secondary metabolites found in plants or plants are generally flavonoids, saponins, quinones, triterpenoids, tannins, steroids, and alkaloids (Humairah et al., 2022). Active compounds contained in various types of plants can be used for treatment in terms of health. In Siregar et al. (2022) explained that plants that contain terpenes have osteoprotective bioactivity. Plants that contain flavonoids have antiosteoporosis bioactivity, and plants with alkaloid content have bioactivity which also acts as antiosteoporosis.

Here are some previous studies proving the potential of various plant extracts for osteoporotic bone repair. In the research of Saleh et al. (2024), showed that the high mineral content in *Cichorium intybus* L. and *Portulaca oleracea* L. extracts significantly improved serum Ca levels, BMD, BMC, and bone index. In addition, both extracts were able to restore trabecular connectivity, bone strength, and bone volume by increasing trabecular and cortical bone thickness and BV/TV%. In Zhang et al. (2016), pomegranate seed aqueous extract was able to repair trabecular bone loss caused by impaired calcium homeostasis due to dexamethasone induction. Furthermore, the administration of *Spilanthes acmella* in the research of Laswati et al. (2015) showed an increase in the average number of trabecular bone osteoblast cells in osteoporosis model male mice due to the effects of phytotestosterone contained in the plant. In the research of Galanis et al. (2019), administration of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* root methanol extract significantly protected tibia BMD loss. In the research of Wu et al. (2019), *Sargassum integerrimum* extract prevented bone loss in oestrogen-deficient rats with hyperlipidaemia. Moreover, no adverse effects were observed after long-term administration of this extract.

From some of these research gaps, it can be concluded that herbal plants are a rich source of medicinal compounds that can be used to prevent osteoporosis. Many animal and cell studies have been conducted to demonstrate the antiosteoporotic effects of various plant extracts and their bioactive compounds. It should be noted that the use of glucocorticoid drugs has significant side effects that affect bone. In addition, according to Maliza et al. (2024), the growth and development of bone tissue is influenced by nutrients and hormones that affect growth rate, bone formation, and bone size. Kastella et al. (2024) stated that the need for calcium and protein must be met early because the average bone growth will stop at the age of 16-18 years.

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